

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D2.2

INVENTORY OF RELEVANT EXTRACTIVE PROJECTS

Summary:

An inventory of extractive projects in Europe addressing socio-economic and environmental impacts, land use planning, health & safety, reporting and permitting, including the results of the mapping and pre-screening for good practises.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fostering the transition to a more sustainable European extractives industry is at the core of the SUMEX project. Work Package 2 (Clustering and Meta-analysis) builds on the results of WP1 (Sustainable Development Framework) and performs a meta-analysis of all relevant European research projects and industry guidance to compile good practices that are fed into a digital repository, a part of the SUMEX toolkit. The meta-analysis lays the groundwork for SUMEX to ultimately produce the most comprehensive stock-taking of sustainability practices in the European extractives sector. These practices will help inform practitioners, be they companies or policy-makers, to make more informed choices and enable a sustainability transition throughout the extractives sector itself.

Compiling the good practices occurs in two steps:

- via a meta-analysis, the first step in the SUMEX project towards building a knowledge base for a sustainable extractives sector in Europe and
- through the subsequent mapping of good practices using a taxonomy developed in WP3 (Policy Analysis) within SUMEX

The meta-analysis is the focus of Task 2.1 (Meta-Analysis and Inventory of Extractives and Related Projects) and initially uses the five SUMEX thematic areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, permitting and policy integration, and reporting of official statistics – to identify and classify the relevant research projects and industry materials. Subsequent screenings utilise the sustainability criteria established in WP1 and the analytical framework (synonymous with the taxonomy mentioned above) from WP3. The projects screened include those granted money under EU funding mechanisms such as H2020, EIT Raw Materials, the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social and Cohesion Fund as well as nationally and regionally funded projects across Europe. Selected industry and professional association practices including those from Anglo American, BHP, Boliden, the European Aggregates Industry (UEPG), the Finnish Network for Sustainable Mining, the International Council of Mining and Metals and Rio Tinto were also screened.

The results of the meta-analysis in Task 2.1, specifically the identified extractives and sustainability-related projects and industry practices, are then combined with the key findings of the two clustering workshops (Task 2.2) and mapped as part of Task 2.3 (Mapping and pre-screening) in the taxonomy provided by WP3, a screenshot of which is directly below. The taxonomy was designed to help practitioners and policy makers easily identify relevant practices for the sustainability of the extractive industry as a whole, and more concretely, those that will initiate learning and drive change. During the mapping process it became clear that not all of the relevant information falls neatly into a category of ‘actionable’ practices, the primary definition WP2 uses to identify practices. Hence, there is also a separate but almost identical taxonomy for what are termed ‘contributing knowledge data items’. Initially an Excel spreadsheet was used to organise the inventory; however, WP3 has since developed the digital repository, and the information in the Excel inventory will now be uploaded into the digital repository. In addition, the screening of practices and contributing knowledge data items will continue under WP4 (Digital Toolkit for Good Practice Guidance and Training). With respect to the categories within the taxonomy, their development and meaning, all of these are explained in detail in Deliverable 3.1: Analytical Framework. For more information, please consult that deliverable.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

Project acronym - short title (optional)	Data item title (practice)	Basic descriptive info							Search criteria					
		Short description [data item/document summary or executive summary etc]	Source of short description (please copy-paste text, abstracts, executive summary the short description is based on)	Year published	SOURCE: page numbers	Document title	Hyperlink (Cordis preferred - website to host the reports/documents)	Format of data items (videos, reports/documents)	Reference to policy	Relevance for good practice learning and case study, report	Extractive sector mine life-cycle stage (i) pre-exploitation phase	SUMEX Focus areas (a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	Commodity type & extractive sector	Industry / business versus public policy context
<p>Erzberg Real-Time Mineral Entry Analysis for Efficient and Sustainable Mining</p>	<p>Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: X-MINE Task 3.2 develops an algorithm for mineral sorting based on data fusion map and configurable user parameters. There are two separate development steps and the first version of the algorithm is introduced in this deliverable D3.2 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors, whereas the second version of the algorithm will be reported in the upcoming D3.3 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - X-MINE sensors. The first version is based on conventional image processing tools such as thresholding, background removal, edge detection and labelling, and it will be tested with the reference samples collected from the participating mines. Samples will be analysed and labelled by experts, and the algorithm improved based on results if needed. The second phase introduces a more developed version of the algorithm, which will be based on more sophisticated methods, such as unsupervised or supervised pattern recognition, 3D model fitting and data fusion methods (the second version of the algorithm will be reported in D3.3 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - X-MINE sensors). This deliverable concentrates on the first version of the algorithm.</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: First, the deliverable describes the image sorting principle and algorithms based on existing sensors. Second, it proceeds to give an overview of the sorting research prototype. It then describes the details of the test procedure including the generation of labels for reference samples.</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: -The X-Mine project (Grant Agreement No. 730270) started on the 1st of June 2017 and will have a 36-month duration, finalizing on the 31st of May 2020. The present D3.2 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors deliverable is related to X-Mine Project's Work package 3: Online Analysis & Sensor based Sorting and to task 3.2: Developing the algorithm for mineral sorting. The objectives of this task can be summarized as follows based on the Description of Action (Part A): - The task will develop an algorithm for mineral sorting based on data fusion map and configurable user parameters. - The task will use calibrated data (i.e. data collected from the scanning of reference sample ore materials) sets to test the algorithm before it is integrated in the hardware solution. Reference samples are collected from the participating mines and experts will analyse the reference samples and label them. The project could also use the mineral collections of SGU or acquire reference samples from other sources. - The first version of the algorithm will be based on conventional image processing tools such as thresholding, background removal, edge detection and labelling. - The first version will be tested with the reference samples, and improved if needed. - The second version of the algorithm will be based on more sophisticated methods, such as unsupervised or supervised pattern recognition, 3D model fitting and data fusion methods. This deliverable is the first of two deliverables on mineral sorting algorithms and describes the first version of the mineral sorting algorithm that is based on existing</p>	2018	X-Mine D3.2 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors. P. 1, 2-30, 31	X-Mine D3.2 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730270/abstract	reports/documents					Unspecified	Industry (and researchers developing new technologies for industry)
<p>SLIM - Sustainable Low Impact Mining Solution for exploitation of small mineral deposits based on advanced rock blasting and environmental technologies</p>	<p>Best Practices on Social Awareness Communication</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: The deliverable analyses best practices for social awareness communication. It does so by first introducing six case studies illustrating six different scenarios. These case studies chosen for the deliverable are Erzberg Mine (Austria), Luján mine (Spain), El Ajbe quarry (Spain), Bor (Serbia), Tärpö (Finland), Cerejón mine (Colombia) and Tierras Raras Muzas (Spain). It then proceeds to give recommendations on how companies can improve their social awareness communication.</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: The key recommendations identified in this practice suggest that companies pay attention to identifying the stakeholders, responding to their demands and meeting their expectations, reporting on CSR/sustainability issues, analysing materiality, obtaining and maintaining SLO through effective stakeholder engagement, integrating the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, defining a communication strategy, integrating communications to enhance sustainability efforts at internal and external level, adopting new technologies and social media for communication matters, monitoring the impacts of the implemented strategies, investing in partnerships and supporting local employment and local communities.</p> <p>What is the expected impact of the practice: The</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: -1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY This is the deliverable number 10.1 elaborated by ZABALA. The document is a report on best practice analysis for communication procedure based on six mining scenarios that are relevant use cases on social awareness. ZABALA identified 6 different scenarios to consider studying and to build up on them a use case. Based on that use cases, an analysis has been carried out to identify good practices on social communication between the mining companies/sites with the local communities affected by its activity and other stakeholders. These good practices aim to promote dialogue and a better understanding between mining companies and local communities and to contribute to obtain the "Social License to Operate (SLO)" of the mining companies reducing the negative impact of its activities and increasing the positive ones, establishing a path to act with due diligence. The present report introduces the situation of the business enterprises focusing on the mining sector in terms of due diligence on human rights and social communication and dialogue with stakeholders, presents the scenarios and case studies used to obtain good practices and generate recommendations on social communication with local communities to mining companies. [...] The mining sites considered in the study are the following: - Erzberg mine (Austria) This site responds to a scenario of a big open pit mine (iron mine) with a lot of years of production and activity situated very closely to the</p>	2018	SLIM D10.1 Best Practices on Social Awareness Communication. p. 4, 7, 20-23	SLIM D10.1 Best Practices on Social Awareness Communication	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/730270/abstract	reports/documents	UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights UN framework of "Protect, Respect and Remedy" AA1000 Stakeholder Engagement Standard (2015)	Guidelines/recommendations	all stages	socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	Unspecified	industry

FIGURE 1: GOOD PRACTICES FROM RESEACH PROJECTS

This report, *Deliverable 2.2: Inventory of Relevant Extractive Projects in Europe*, provides the meta-analysis methodology used to screen projects and relevant deliverables and the mapping methodology to subsequently map good practices that will be included in the SUMEX digital repository. A summary of the number of projects, deliverables and industry practices screened is provided below.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF ALL SCREENINGS

	H2014-2015	H 2016-2017	H2018-2020	National / Regional Projects	Industry Good Practices
No. of projects screened	19	32	6	56	
No. deliverable screened	22	35	4	72	
No. of industries/associations screened					6
No. of industry/association documents screened					45
Total Inventory = 275 practices and contributing knowledge data items					

In order to access the inventory in the Excel spreadsheet, please use the following link: https://www.sumexproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/SUMEX_MetaAnalysis_Inventory.xlsx

2 INTRODUCTION

The meta-analysis conducted in Work Package 2 (WP2) is the first step towards building a knowledge base of sustainable practices for the European extractives industry and forms the foundation for the other work packages in the SUMEX project to build on. SUMEX’s five thematic areas - socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, permitting and policy integration, and reporting official statistics – were used as the initial screening criteria for projects granted money under European Union (EU) funding mechanisms including H2020, EIT Raw Materials, the European Regional Development Fund, and the European Social and Cohesion Fund as well as national and regional projects across Europe. Selected industry guidance is also screened. The methodology consists of a systematic approach that identifies and screens (section 3: meta-analysis) and subsequently structures data (section 4: mapping and pre-screening).

Structuring the data is via a taxonomy designed by WP3 that guides the identification and mapping of good practices and was designed according to the relevance for good practice learning and the extractive sector mine life-cycle stage. The inventory that comprises D2.2 uses an Excel spreadsheet (https://www.sumexproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/SUMEX_MetaAnalysis_Inventory.xlsx) to organise the data, but once the digital repository is functioning, the inventory will then be uploaded to the repository. The intent is to continue the screenings so the repository will be a living entity for the duration of the SUMEX project. A pilot repository with 80 practices was created at the end of September to test the design of the digital repository. The roll-out of the digital repository will be in April 2022.

A quality control mechanism was introduced to ensure the mapping is both accurate and relevant and entails a review by WP4. The actual identification of what are considered good practices in the SUMEX context occurs in WP3. The following sections describe the methodology used for the meta-analysis and mapping processes in more detail.

3 META-ANALYSIS

Task 2.1 (Meta-Analysis and Inventory of Extractives and Related Projects) uses the five SUMEX thematic areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessment, land use planning, health and safety, permitting and policy integration, and reporting of official statistics – to identify and classify relevant European research projects and industry guidance. Subsequent screenings utilise the sustainability criteria established in WP1 and the taxonomy from WP3. The projects screened include those that were granted money under EU funding mechanisms such as H2020, EIT Raw Materials, the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social and Cohesion Fund as well as nationally and regionally funded projects across Europe. Selected industry and professional association practices including those from Anglo American, BHP, Boliden, the European Aggregates Industry (UEPG), the Finnish Network for Sustainable Mining, the International Council of Mining and Metals and Rio Tinto were also screened.

3.1 SCREENING EU LEVEL PROJECTS

Two main sources were used to identify relevant EU level extractives and extractives-related projects:

1. The Horizon 2020 Societal Challenge 5 (Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials) Work Programmes for 2014-2015, 2016-2017 and 2018-2020.
2. D9.2 Final List of Projects at the International Level from the MIREU (Mining and Metallurgy Regions EU) project which already screened extractives-related projects for good practices from the following sources: EIT Raw Materials, Interreg Europe, ERA-NET and all Horizon 2020 funding calls including Research and Innovation Actions, Innovation Actions, Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, Coordinating and Support Actions and ERC Consolidator Grants.

H2020 and MIREU D9.2 documents were screened with the qualitative data analysis tool, NVIVO, to find relevant sub-calls and projects in the fields of extractives, climate, waste, water innovation, Earth observation, policy and innovation. For the screening process, SUMEX’s thematic areas - (1) health & safety (2) land-use planning (3) reporting (4) permitting processes and policy integration (5) socio-economic and environmental impacts - were used as nodes. A node (please see Figure 2 below) is a collection of references about a specific theme or case. All references that mentioned one or more thematic areas were coded with the relevant node or nodes. The coding reports can be provided for further use.

Nodes				
Name	Files	References	Created On	
Health & Safety		1	12	4.2.2021 15.22
Land use planning		1	5	4.2.2021 15.22
Permitting processes & Policy Integration		1	22	4.2.2021 15.23
Reporting		1	1	4.2.2021 15.22
Socio-economic & Environmental Impacts		1	16	4.2.2021 15.23

FIGURE 2: NVIVO NODES

To show the NVIVO screening report in a readable form, all identified H2020 sub-calls are listed in a Word document (Figure 3). Under each sub-call are the references showing why this exact sub-call was chosen and

which parts of the call text match with the search words. The phrases around the actual keywords are included in the document to give the reader a context of the search word. This approach supports a transparent screening process and allows external actors to review different stages of the meta-analysis.

FIGURE 3: NVIVO SCREENING REPORT

Screening with priority areas and additional search criteria

As an experiment, Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials H2020 Work Programme 2016-2017 was then screened using different search words and nodes. The first stage of the second screening was carried out using the draft D1.2 priority areas provided by WP1. The second stage of screening was conducted using additional words WP2 considered potentially useful search criteria to provide a more detailed approach. The search words/nodes were changed the following way:

- Circular economy instead of Closed Cycles (WP1)
- Mining in Ecosystem Services instead of Assigning Value to Biological Capital (WP1)
- Mining Landscapes (added)
- Stakeholders and Civil Society (added under Accountability)
- Public Policy, Social Licence to Operate and Social Acceptance (in addition to Corporate Social Responsibility – WP1)
- Post-mining Land use (added)
- Innovation

One of the conclusions of the two coding reports is that the WP1 priority areas are not detailed enough for WP2’s purposes. For example, based on the number of times additional nodes such as stakeholders, social licence to operate (11 hits), public policy (35), social acceptance (8) and innovation (48) were mentioned, the original priority areas lacked detail. The opposite occurred when more precise yet thematically broad search words were used as they captured every single project. The most useful screening simply used the SUMEX thematic areas as this pulled up the relevant calls and excluded the extraneous ones.

Nodes				
Name	Files	References	Created On	
⊖ Circular Economy		1	26	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Biological		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Mining in ecosystem services		1	11	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Mining landscapes		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Technological		1	9	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Sharing, leasing, reuse, repair..		1	7	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Corporate Social Responsibility, Social License to Operate		1	47	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Accountability		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ External and social costs		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Life Cycle Analysis		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Public-private partnerships		1	1	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Developing Criteria		1	1	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Civil society		1	6	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Stakeholders		1	24	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Public Policy		1	35	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Social License to Operate		1	11	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Social Acceptance		1	8	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Dialogue and Communication		1	48	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Control over the environment		0	0	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Share knowledge		1	24	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Sustainable learning		1	1	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Reinventing the economy (i.e. Green Deal)		1	53	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Indicators of Green Economy		1	1	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Innovation		1	48	20.1.2021 15.18
⊖ Natural capital - financial capital		1	4	20.1.2021 15.18

FIGURE 4: AN EXAMPLE OF NVIVO NODES, ADDITIONAL PRIORITY AREAS

Ultimately, for the actual screening, WP2 used the SUMEX D1.2 criteria (p. 17) as well as an additional list of synonyms as search words and nodes. Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials H2020 Work Programmes 2014-2015, 2016-2017 and 2018-2020 programs and MIREU D9.2 were rescreened with the search words presented in the table below. The table includes the five SUMEX themes (headline), D1.2 priority area categories (first column), D1.2 priority area subcategories (second column) and the actual search words, as well as additional search words (third column), used to screen the documents.

TABLE 2: FINAL LIST OF SEARCH WORDS FOR THE SCREENING

1. Health & Safety		
Reinventing the economy		
Social and societal responsibility	Improving workers' well-being	Wellbeing/Well-being
		Health & Safety
		Zero harm
		Improved skills
Environmental sustainability		

2. Land use planning		
Reinventing the economy	Extractives' role in closing cycles	Recycle, reuse, redesign, reduction
		Closing cycles
		Biological/technological reduction
		Dematerialisation
		Redesign
		Post-consumerism
	Planning beyond the mine life	Post-materialism
		Post-closure
		Closing Rehabilitation
Social and societal responsibility	Developing value together with society	Collaboration
		Consultation
		Cooperation
		Social Licence to Operate
		Social acceptability
		Social Capital
		Natural Capital
		Participation
Environmental sustainability	Multiple, co-operative land use	Land use / land-use
		Landscape
		Land use conflicts
		Net positive impact
		Ecosystem (services) Biodiversity
	Integrated water management	Integrated Water management
	Enlightened waste management	Waste management
		Circular economy
		Recycling
		Secondary waste streams Valorisation of waste
3. Reporting		
Reinventing the economy	Understanding of the role and indicators for extractives	International standards Good practice
Social and societal responsibility	Sustainable learning	Sustainable learning
		Systems thinking
		Learning feedback loops
	Share knowledge and information	Transparency
Share/sharing Knowledge/information		
Environmental sustainability		
4. Permitting processes and Policy integration		
Reinventing the economy	Benefit Sharing	Benefit sharing
		Shared value
		Accountability
		Life-cycle considerations
		Reporting
		Natural capital
	Share knowledge and information transparently	Share/sharing Knowledge/information

Social and societal responsibility	Social capital	Social capital
	Taking responsibility for goods and services	Responsibility Green Economy
Environmental sustainability		
5. Socio-economic and environmental impacts		
Reinventing the economy	Valuing natural and social capital	Natural capital
		Social capital
		Social Licence to Operate
		Social cohesion
	Accountability	Accountability
		Life-cycle
	Extractives' role in closing cycles	Recycle, reuse, redesign, reduction
		Closing cycles
		Biological/technological
	Planning beyond the mine life	Post-closure
		Rehabilitation
		Closing
Social and societal responsibility	Developing value together with society	Collaboration
		Consultation
		Cooperation
		Social Licence to Operate
		Social acceptability
		Social Capital
		Natural Capital
	Participation	
Community well-being	Wellbeing/Well-being	
Environmental sustainability	Integrated water management	Integrated water management
	Efficient energy consumption	Energy consumption
		Renewable energy
		Greenhouse gas emissions (reduction)
	Multiple, co-operative land use	Land use/ land-use
		Landscape
		Land use conflicts
		Net positive impact
		Ecosystem (services)
		Biodiversity
	Enlightened waste management	Waste management
		Circular economy
		Recycling
		Secondary waste streams
		Valorisation of waste
Community well-being	Wellbeing/Well-being	

3.1.1 IDENTIFYING RELEVANT DELIVERABLES

Based on the results from the screening, WP2 compiled a list of relevant H2020 sub-calls which were then used as search words to identify the actual projects in Cordis, the European Commission’s online database of all Horizon projects. Once the exhaustive list of EU level projects was compiled, the next step was to identify project deliverables that would ultimately be screened for good practices. These deliverables were pulled out and uploaded into an external database.

Please see Figure 5 for an example of the tables used to organise and track the screened deliverables. A total of 57 EU level projects and 61 deliverables were screened.

Project	Deliverable (https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1WWB9pla5POeg585xC1AQsQ_rh1CgZlye)	Screened Deliverables
BioDivScen	D6.3 Handbook on the use of biodiversity scenarios in support of decision-making	D6.3 Handbook on the use of biodiversity scenarios in support of decision-making
CHROMIC	D6.4 Community Involvement Plan	D6.4 Community Involvement Plan
CIRCULAR IMPACTS	Insights from the CIRCULAR IMPACTS case studies	Insights from the CIRCULAR IMPACTS case studies
COLLECTORS	Deliverable 2.4 Report on solutions for tackling systemic and technical boundary conditions	Deliverable 2.4 Report on solutions for tackling systemic and technical boundary conditions

FIGURE 5: HORIZON PROJECTS AND DELIVERABLES 2016-2017 SCREENED (EXTRACT)

3.2 SCREENING NATIONAL AND REGIONAL PROJECTS

Nationally and regionally funded projects across the European Union were also screened according to the five core thematic areas of SUMEX. The projects primarily consist of those funded by EIT Raw Materials, Interreg Europe, European Investment and Structural Funds (EISF), the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD). At times language posed a challenge as a number of these projects had websites and deliverables produced in their native language, but the majority were still in English. A total of 56 projects and 72 reports were screened.

All screened documents can be found in the SUMEX online repository in https://www.sumexproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/SUMEX_MetaAnalysis_Inventory.xlsx

TABLE 3: NATIONAL & REGIONAL PROJECTS SCREENED (EXTRACT)

REGIONAL PROJECTS				
Project	Funding	Relevant Deliverables/Documents	Screened deliverables/documents	Links
Abenteuer Erzberg	ESIF, EAFRD	Abenteuer Erzberg	Abenteuer Erzberg	
ADRIANA Remote sensing detection of industrial recyclables in mine tailings	Ministry of Education and Research	ADRIANA	ADRIANA Remote sensing detection of industrial recyclables in mine tailings	https://www.bmbf-client.de/sites/default/files/2021/07/ADRIANA_remote_sensing_detection_of_industrial_recyclables_in_mine_tailings.pdf
Africa Mining Vision	GIZ	Africa Mining Vision	Africa Mining Vision	https://au.int/en/ti/amv/about
ARCHUB2	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	ARCHUB2	Arctic Network Hub	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/archub2
Arctic Geoinvest	ESIF, ERDF	Arctic Geoinvest (webpage)	Arctic Geoinvest (webpage)	https://www.maanmittauslaitos.fi/en/responsible-mining
Arctic Smartness projects	ESIF, ERDF	Arctic Industry and Circular Economy cluster (webpage)	Arctic Industry and Circular Economy cluster (webpage)	Arctic Smart Rural Community Arctic Smartness
ARIDuA	ESIF, ESF	ARIDuA	ARIDuA	https://tu-freiberg.de/en/aridua
BestBioPLA		BestBioPLA Fully Bio-based PLA Composites with Long-term Durability	BestBioPLA Fully Bio-based PLA Composites with Long-term Durability	https://www.bmbf-client.de/en/projects/bestbiopla
BioLeach	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	BioLeach	Innovative Bio-treatment of RM	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/bioleach
Biopeitto	ESIF, ERDF	Biopeitto-projekti. Biohiilien hyödyntäminen kaivannaisjätteiden peittomateriaaleissa ja viherrakentamisessa	Biopeitto-projekti. Biohiilien hyödyntäminen kaivannaisjätteiden peittomateriaaleissa ja viherrakentamisessa (https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/51_2021)	https://www.gtk.fi/tutkimusprojekti/biopeitto
BioProLat		BioProLat	BioProLat Reductive Bioprocessing to Recover Cobalt and Nickel From Late	BioProLat – Reductive Bioprocessing to Recover
BrineMine Extracting minerals and drinking water from geothermal sources	Brine Mine	BrineMine	BrineMine Extracting minerals and drinking water from geothermal sources	https://www.bmbf-client.de/sites/default/files/2021/07/BrineMine_extracting_minerals_and_drinking_water_from_geothermal_sources.pdf
BuSK	ESIF, Interreg	Local Acceptance of Industrial Operations Within Mining, Forest and Agriculture BUILDING SHARED KNOWLEDGE CAPITAL TO SUPPORT NATURAL RESOURCES	Local Acceptance of Industrial Operations Within Mining, Forest and Agriculture BUILDING SHARED KNOWLEDGE CAPITAL TO SUPPORT NATURAL RESOURCES	https://busk.interreg-npa.eu
CAMaRSEC	Ministry of Education and Research	CAMaRSEC	CAMaRSEC Climate-adapted Material Research for the Socio-economic Con	https://www.bmbf-client.de/en/projekte/camarsec
CaMona	Ministry of Education and Research	CaMona	CaMona	https://www.bmbf-client.de/en/projects/camona
DAMAST Technologies for the safe and efficient operation of water reservoirs	Ministry of Education and Research	DAMAST	DAMAST Technologies for the safe and efficient operation of water reservoirs	https://www.bmbf-client.de/sites/default/files/2021/07/DAMAST_technologies_for_the_safe_and_efficient_operation_of_water_reservoirs.pdf
DIM ESEE				https://www.rgn.unizg.hr/en/studies/lifeandenvironment
DIM ESEE 2	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	Website	DIM ESEE-2 (website)	HOME DUBROVNIK INTERNATIONAL ESEE
DUB-GEM	Ministry of Education and Research	DUB-GEM	Aerial Mapping – Radioactive Contamination in Central Asia	https://www.bmbf-client.de/sites/default/files/2021/07/DUB-GEM_aerial_mapping_radioactive_contamination_in_central_asia.pdf
EnEx	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	EnEx	Enhanced exploration	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/enex/
FARMIN	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	FARMIN	Field Augmented Reality in Mineral Exploration and Mining	
GeRI: The Global Commodity Initiative				
GloREIA	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	GloREIA	Towards a Global Rare Earth Industry Association	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/gloreia
HoloMine	EIT Regional Innovation Scheme	HoloMine	Mixed Reality in Mining	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/holomine
Passiiviset hybridipuhdistusratkaisut arktisten valumavesien typpipitoisuuden vähentämiseksi	ESIF, ERDF	https://helda.helsinki.fi/handle/10138/30000	Passiiviset hybridipuhdistusratkaisut arktisten valumavesien typpipitoisuuden vähentämiseksi	

4 MAPPING AND PRE-SCREENING

Task 2.3 is the mapping and pre-screening of good practices extracted from the deliverables identified in Task 2.1 and also from the clustering workshops conducted as part of Task 2.2. After compilation of the deliverables, the taxonomy provided by WP3 (please see D3.1: Analytical Framework) was applied to the practices so they would align not only substantively with the WP3 analysis of case studies, but also be in a format that could easily be replicated in the online repository (WP4).

The starting point of the taxonomy was defining what a real practice is and there are two perspectives:

- Impact – what is the impact /does it really contribute to Sustainable Development
- Guidance and informing decision-making – does it provide an actual instrument, tool, service, or product or help with a particular decision-making process

This ultimately influenced the organisation of the final inventory as there are two categories of data relevant for the identification of practice: the first are ‘actionable’ practices, or those that can be tangibly implemented, and the second category consists of knowledge that can help to implement practices or what are called ‘contributing knowledge data items’ in the taxonomy. The taxonomy itself has been designed in accordance with the data contained in the European Commission’s Raw Material Information System (RMIS) making it accessible should the Commission want to import practices directly from the repository into the RMIS. Against this background, the EC JRC (European Commission Joint Research Centre) respective experts on the extractives sector and mineral resources have been consulted to bring in line as much as possible the project understanding of a workable taxonomy with the RMIS glossary terms, definitions and taxonomy. Once the taxonomy was established and the mapping underway, design of the digital repository (WP4) began and 80 practices were provided for the pilot repository at the end of September 2021.

The pre-screening of the project data is synonymous with the quality control mechanism mentioned in the Introduction. To ensure the mapping is both accurate and relevant, on a weekly basis, approximately 15-20 practices and/or knowledge items were compiled by the WP2 team and then submitted to the WP4 team who conducted an initial quality screening. The inventory was then handed over to WP3 for further policy analysis and actual incorporation into the toolkit developed as part of WP4. The further policy analysis consists of applying the sustainability criteria from Deliverable 1.2 and the leverage points concept, discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.1, to the inventory. While the taxonomy elaborated in D3.1 provided a common understanding of concepts such as mine or quarry life cycle or sustainability, the actual quality check has been carried out by experts of SUMEX partner organisations LAY, WUW and MUL in the respective WPs (WP2, WP3, and WP4). The technical implementation of an online system for describing project data will help to avoid any errors in terms of format, structure or data transfer among the involved experts and partner organisations. For that purpose, the WUW team provided test-runs, feedback cycles and technical manuals to experts in partner organisations for proper conduct and handling of the technical platform. In order to guarantee integrity and data security, the necessary measures have been undertaken to prevent any misuse (e.g. two-factor authentication). On a weekly basis, the project partner WUW coordinates and approves the correct use of data upload and manages the description of data items among different project partners. The following sections describe the methodology used for the mapping process in more detail.

4.1 MAPPING ACTIONABLE PRACTICE DATA ITEMS

Actionable practices are those that can actually be implemented whether by a practitioner or policy-maker and most of the inventory is comprised of these. The taxonomy for the actionable practices is provided in Table 4 and the categories are described in detail in Deliverable 3.1.

TABLE 4: TAXONOMY FOR ACTIONABLE PRACTICES

Column	Taxonomy Description
A	Project acronym & short title
B	Data item title (practice)
C	Short description (data item/document summary or executive summary etc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge the practice is addressing • Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal • What is the expected impact of the practice • Who is the target user group of the practice/intervention or implementing the practice/intervention
D	Short description – the difference in this column from that of Column C is that the information is to be copy and pasted from the original source <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge the practice is addressing • Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal • What is the expected impact of the practice • Who is the target user group of the practice/intervention or implementing the practice/intervention
E	Year published
F	SOURCE: page numbers
G	Document title
H	Hyperlink (Cordis preferred - website to enter the data item directly or download it)
I	Format of data items (videos, repository & resource libraries and toolkits, reports/document, websites)
J	Reference to policy
K	Relevance for good practice learning and training (case study, Handbooks, Guidance documents, training materials/MOOC/webinar, Toolkits, courses)
L	Extractive sector mine life-cycle stage (i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), (ii) exploration, (iii) pre-exploitation/ development stage (e.g. feasibility study), (iv) exploitation phase, (v) post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)
M	SUMEX Focus areas (a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, (b) land use planning, (c) health and safety, (d) reporting official statistics, (e) permitting processes/policy integration
N	Commodity type & extractive sector <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Iron and Ferro-Alloy Metals 2) Non-Ferrous Metals - Rare Earth Elements 3) Precious, rare and high-tech Metals 4) Industrial Minerals 5) Mineral Fuels 6) Unspecified
O	Industry / business versus public policy context

Figure 6 below shows an example of the actionable practices mapped into the taxonomy and Excel spreadsheet.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

The taxonomy for industry good practices is the same as that for research projects. Figure 7 below shows an example of the industry practice mapping.

Basic descriptive info												Search criteria			
Project acronym + short title (optional)	Data item title (practice)	Short description (data item/document summary or executive summary etc)	Source of short description (please copy-paste text, abstracts, executive summary the short description is based on)	Year published	SOURCE: page numbers	Document title	hyperlink (Cordis preferred - website to enter the data item directly or download it)	format of data items (videos, repository & resource libraries and toolkits, reports/document, websites)	Reference to policy	Relevance for good practice learning and training (case study, Handbooks, Guidance documents, training materials/MOOC/w	Extractive sector mine life-cycle stage (i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), ii) exploration, iii) pre-exploitation/development stage	SUMEX Focus areas (a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, b) land use planning, c) health and safety, d) reporting official statistics, e)	Commodity type & extractive sector 1) Iron and Ferro-Alloy Metals 2) Non-Ferrous Metals - Rare Earth Elements 3) Precious, rare and	Industry / business versus public policy context	
BHP	Community Requirements	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: Community engagement is an important factor for achieving acceptance among communities and regions affected by mining activities. Community Requirements document describes the principles and activities necessary to implement to minimise negative social and human rights impacts from BHP activities.</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: The document provides employees guidance on how to engage with communities, plan for community development activities, and how to implement practices that commit to human rights principles as well as preserving cultural heritage. The concrete practices include, for example, conducting a social baseline study to assess social, economic, political and environmental aspects of relevant communities, in addition, a social impact and opportunity assessment to identify gaps and opportunities for community engagement.</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: 'Why is this important? We believe in developing strong, mutually beneficial relationships with communities, regions and countries where we do business and contributing to their economic and social development. We also understand and minimise adverse social and human rights impacts from our activities.'</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: Understanding our host communities To inform community engagement, community development and business plans we must understand the social and economic environment and identify and analyse stakeholders, social impacts and business risks.</p> <p>Every five years:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the boundaries of host communities impacted by BHP's operations. • Complete and update a social baseline study to assess the social, economic, political, security and environmental aspects of these communities. The study must include quality-of-life indicators that may be used to track progress over time. 	2018	BHP: Community Requirements, P. 1-7	Community Requirements	https://www.bhp.com/-/media/documents/ourapproach/governance/180529_community.pdf?la=en	Report/document	<p>ICMM Position Statement on Indigenous Peoples</p> <p>IFC Performance Standard 5: Land Acquisition and Involuntary Resettlement</p> <p>United Nations Declaration of Human Rights</p>	Guidance documents	All stages	socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	any commodity	Industry/business	
BHP	BHP - Community Requirements	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: Mining activities can generate negative social impacts on local communities. BHP Community Requirements is a guidance document that helps company employees and contractors to consider all necessary community related aspects when conducting mining activities.</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: BHP Community Requirements state that every five years the social, economic, political, security and environmental aspects of communities affected by BHP activities are to be assessed. BHP carries out a community perception survey every three years to guide them with their stakeholder engagement measures. The document gives guidance on how to engage with communities, and how to plan,</p>	<p>Challenge the practice is addressing: 'Why is this important? We believe in developing strong, mutually beneficial relationships with communities, regions and countries where we do business and contributing to their economic and social development. We also understand and minimise adverse social and human rights impacts from our activities.'</p> <p>Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal: 'Understanding our host communities To inform community engagement, community development and business plans we must understand the social and economic environment and identify and analyse stakeholders, social impacts and business risks.</p> <p>Every five years:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define the boundaries of host communities impacted by BHP's operations. • Complete and update a social baseline study to assess 	2018	BHP - Community Requirements	BHP - Community Requirements	https://www.bhp.com/-/media/documents/ourapproach/governance/180529_community.pdf?la=en	reports/documents	<p>United Nations Universal Declaration on Human Rights</p> <p>Global Compact</p> <p>ICMM Position Statement on Indigenous Peoples and Mining</p> <p>IFC Performance Standard 5: Land Acquisition and Involuntary Resettlement</p>	guidance documents	(i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), ii) exploration, iii) pre-exploitation/development stage (e.g. feasibility study), iv) exploitation phase, v) post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation))	{ a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	any commodity	Industry	

FIGURE 7: MAPPING INDUSTRY GOOD PRACTICES

4.2 MAPPING CONTRIBUTING KNOWLEDGE DATA ITEMS

For the contributing knowledge data items inventory, the taxonomy is essentially the same with the exception of two columns that were deleted - column D (short description) and column G (document).

TABLE 5: TAXONOMY FOR CONTRIBUTING KNOWLEDGE DATA ITEMS

Column	Taxonomy Description
A	Project acronym & short title
B	Data item title (practice)
C	Short description (data item/document summary or executive summary etc) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge the practice is addressing • Concrete practice/intervention to achieve the expected goal • What is the expected impact of the practice • Who is the target user group of the practice/intervention or implementing the practice/intervention
E	Year published
F	SOURCE: page numbers
H	Hyperlink (Cordis preferred - website to enter the data item directly or download it)
I	Format of data items (videos, repository & resource libraries and toolkits, reports/document, websites)

This inventory contains both research and industry data items.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

Basic descriptive info										Search criteria			
Project acronym - short title (optional)	Data item title (knowledge contributor)	Short description (data item/document summary or executive summary etc)	Year published	SOURCE: page numbers	hyperlink (Cordis preferred - website to enter the data item directly or download it)	format of data items (videos, repository & resource libraries and toolkits, reports/document websites)	Reference to policy	Relevance for good practice learning and training (case study, Handbooks, Guidance documents)	Extractive sector mine life-cycle stage (i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), ii) exploration, iii) pre-exploitation/development stage	SUMEX Focus areas (a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, b) land use	Commodity type & extractive sector 1) Iron and Ferro-Alloy Metals 2) Mo	Industry / business versus public policy context	
BHP	BHP Code of Conduct - Health and Safety	<p>Challenge being addressed: Working in mining operations can pose certain risks to human health through occupational diseases or injuries. BHP Health and Safety policies give useful guidance and rules to guarantee the safety of employees and visitors at the mine sites.</p> <p>Contributing knowledge for the challenge: BHP Health and Safety commitments are governed by company documents such as Our Requirements for Health, Our Requirements for Safety and Our Requirements for Health, Safety, Environment and Community Reporting, as well as local safety standards. The guidance includes information of people and different departments within BHP that should be contacted in case help is needed. The document also sets expectations</p>	2018	BHP Code of Conduct p. 11, 12	https://www.bhp.com/~/media/documents/our-requirements-for-health-and-safety-en.pdf	reports/document	<p>Company policies:</p> <p>Our Requirements for Health</p> <p>Our Requirements for Safety and Our Requirements for Health, Safety, Environment and Community Reporting</p> <p>Our Requirements for Security and</p>	Guidance documents	(i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), ii) exploration, iii) pre-exploitation/development stage (e.g. feasibility study), iv) exploitation phase, v) post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	c) health and safety	General	Industry/business	
BHP	BHP Code of Conduct - Workplace equality and inclusion	<p>Challenge being addressed: The guidance for workplace equality and inclusion aims to prevent harassment and bullying at BHP operations and to guarantee discrimination free working environment for all employees.</p> <p>Contributing knowledge for the challenge: BHP Workplace equality and inclusion document provides information on departments and people to approach in case an employee experiences discrimination or other kind of harassment at work. The document also states that discrimination based on personal attributes unrelated to job performance is strictly prohibited and</p>	2018	BHP Code of Conduct, p. 13,14	https://www.bhp.com/~/media/documents/our-requirements-for-workplace-equality-and-inclusion-en.pdf	reports/document	<p>Company policies:</p> <p>Our Requirements for Human Resources</p> <p>Our Requirements for Business Conduct (Guidance Note for Retaliation)</p> <p>Employee Assistance Program</p>	Guidance documents	(i) pre-exploration (land-use planning), ii) exploration, iii) pre-exploitation/development stage (e.g. feasibility study), iv) exploitation phase, v) post-exploitation phase (i.e. rehabilitation)	(a) socio-economic and environmental impact assessments	General	Industry/business	

FIGURE 8: CONTRIBUTING KNOWLEDGE DATA ITEMS

4.3 SCREENING INDUSTRY PRACTICES

In addition to regional, national and EU level projects, selected multi-national extractive companies and internationally recognised good practice guidance documents were also selected for screening. As it is primarily the major mining companies who have publicly available documents on their websites, relevant documents matching the five core areas of SUMEX were screened from Anglo American, BHP and Rio Tinto. These three companies were chosen and recommended by the SUMEX consortium partners due to their globally recognised sustainability practices that set the benchmark standard for the extractives industry as a whole. Recognising that international standards also influence industry's sustainable development practices, four of the International Council of Mining and Metals (ICMM) documents and the Toolbox for Local Actions from the Finnish Network for Sustainable Mining were also screened. UEPG's sustainable practice case studies and Boliden's sustainability reports are currently being screened. They will be added to the inventory of WP2 and uploaded to the online user-friendly repository in the near future.

The documents from the three companies, which include primarily sustainability case study examples and suggested policies, as well as ICMM and the Finnish Network for Sustainable Mining, were screened according to the five SUMEX themes, then coded by priority areas and finally a separate screening was conducted using other terms linked to the priority areas (see Table 6). Ultimately information from the industry documents were incorporated into both the actionable practices as well as contributing knowledge inventories.

TABLE 6: INDUSTRY PRACTICES SCREENED (EXTRACT)

Industry Practices	Company/Insitution	Document	Links	Practices screened
	RIOTINTO		https://www.riotinto.com/sus	
		Kaivosvastuujärjestelmä Water management Tailings Management Mine closure Performance Health & Safety Energy Use and GHG Emission Crisis Management Planning Biodiversity Management Community Outreach Performance		Water management Tailings Management Mine closure Performance Health & Safety Crisis Management Energy Use and GHG Emissions Biodiversity Management Community Outreach Performance
	Kaivosvastuu		https://www.kaivosvastuu.fi/k	
		Social Way Toolbox: 3A Stakeholder Engagement 3A Stakeholder Engagement 3B Incident and Grievance Management 3C Social and Human Rights Impact Assessment 4A Socio-Economic Development 4B Contractor Social Management 4C Community Health and Safety 4D Emergency Preparedness 4E Security Management & Protection 4F Land Access, Displacement and Resettlement 4G Site-Induced Migration (SILM) 4H Cultural Heritage 4I Indigenous Peoples 4J Conflict Management 4K Artisanal and Small-Scale Mining		3A Stakeholder Engagement - Community 3A Stakeholder Engagement - Stakeholder 3B Incident and Grievance Management 3C Social and Human Rights Impact Assessment 4A Socio-Economic Development (SE) 4B Contractor Social Management 4C Community Health and Safety Management
	Anglo American		https://socialway.angloameric	
		Code of Conduct Environment and Climate Change Safety - Our Requirements Health - Our Requirements Community - Our Requirements	https://www.bhp.com/-/media https://www.bhp.com/-/media https://www.bhp.com/-/media https://www.bhp.com/-/media https://www.bhp.com/-/media	Environment and Climate Change - Our Safety - Our Requirements Health - Our Requirements Community - Our Requirements Code of Conduct
	BHP			

5 FURTHER MAPPING FOR WP3: SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY CRITERIA AND LEVERAGE POINTS

Fostering a transition towards sustainability in the extractives sector is at the core of the SUMEX project. The conceptualisation of sustainable development (SD) in the extractives sector and the identification of practices was an initial step for a more detailed **framework describing the potential of the extractive sector to be part of a sustainability transition**. However, the meaning and operationalisation of SD has been subject to many different discussions among scholars, experts, and practitioners in public policy, industry and civil society alike. For that purpose, the SUMEX project utilises a number of frameworks that help to identify extractive sector practices in both the business and public sector with the potential to drive change towards sustainability: The SUMEX Sustainability Aspects and the Leverage Points (see D1.2 and D3.1, for more details). These two concepts have been translated into readily available mapping concepts for project data (for more details see D3.1) and, consequently, applied in the actual mapping of practices in order to identify solutions towards sustainability. For that purposes, SUMEX researchers from different disciplines (mining engineering, land use and spatial planning, anthropology and political sciences etc.) work together to identify and describe relevant links to these frameworks and are engaged in continuous feedback and consultation processes to guarantee validity and reliability of data mapping results.

The two concepts will support **practitioners to easily identify practices** in both the business and public policy spheres, and their potential to initiate learning and change as well as their relevance for extractive sector sustainability.

5.1.1 SUMEX SUSTAINABILITY ASPECTS

The SUMEX Sustainability Aspects describe key components of what sustainable management of the extractive industry in Europe should consider. They represent a set of topics (e.g. valuing social and natural capital, planning beyond the mine life) and goals (e.g. no bribes, zero greenhouse gas emissions), which have to be underlined with processes in order to get to such a state. The sustainability aspects consider the European Green Deal and its aspiration to transform the European economy to an inclusive, circular and carbon neutral economy in 2050. As already stated above, they are a mixture of topics which should be considered as part of responsible mineral extraction in the present (e.g. emergency preparedness and risk management, diversity and anti-discrimination) and future aspirations (e.g. defining the role of extractives in a green economy, carbon neutrality) which the sector needs to move towards going forward. The below-mentioned more detailed description of SUMEX Sustainability Aspects is a useful mapping framework for screening project data on its link to certain sustainability topics.

SUMEX Sustainability Aspects on “Transforming the economy“

- “Indicators”; Short description = Understanding of the role and indicators for extractives in an inclusive Green Economy that exists within Planetary Boundaries (incl. innovation for technology “jumps”, new business models, consumption patterns and “needs” considerations)
- “Valuing all forms of capital” = Valuing all forms of capital, i.e. natural and social capital
- “Benefit Sharing” = Defining what Benefit Sharing (or Shared Value) means (beyond taxes and jobs)
- “Accountability” = Accountability (i.e., life-cycle considerations and product labelling, various capitals, reporting)

- “Closing cycles” = Extractives’ role in closing cycles, both biological and technological (beyond recycling, focus on reduction/dematerialisation, multiple use and redesign of products)
- “Planning beyond the mine life” (i.e. clear time horizons, after mine life use, reclamation of land towards prior or societally relevant use, extraction as an enabler for succeeding activities/livelihoods)
- Holistic risk management and emergency preparedness

SUMEX Sustainability Aspects on “Social and societal responsibility”

- “Shared vision of the future” = Partner with host communities and society to deliver a shared vision of the future
- “Stakeholder engagement” = Engage in continuous dialogue with stakeholders, create trusted grievance mechanisms and shared investigation and problem-solving processes
- Safeguard human rights
- “Protect cultural heritage” = Protect cultural heritage, i.e. regarding indigenous people and ensure free, prior and informed consent
- “Ethical corporate practices” = Adhere to ethical corporate practices (no support of corruption, no bribes)
- “Diversity, inclusion & anti-discrimination” (i.e. gender, young and old, indigenous people)
- “Holistic management and continuous learning” = Holistic management and continuous learning (systems thinking, company and site impacts, the ability to learn from mistakes, social/peer learning, reflexivity, continuous monitoring and reporting)
- “Transparent information” = Share data and information transparently (incl. payments and revenues, environmental and social data)
- “workers’ well-being” = Improving workers’ well-being (zero harm, improved skills, fair compensation and terms of work, involvement)

SUMEX Sustainability Aspects on “Environmental sustainability “

- “Integrated water stewardship” = Integrated, watershed-based water stewardship (incl. a focus on water efficiency and avoidance of freshwater use)
- “Efficient energy consumption” = Efficient energy consumption, based on renewable energy
- Carbon neutrality
- Zero harmful air emissions
- “Land use and biodiversity” = Arrangement of different land uses (spatial and temporal) and net positive impact on ecosystem services and biodiversity (incl. from indirect impacts)
- “Advanced waste management” = Advanced waste management (considering secondary resources from traditional waste by-products, zero waste to landfill, no impact on surrounding environment)

5.1.2 LEVERAGE POINTS

Approaches, such as the Leverage Points (LP) are conceptual models to best understand what are ways to introduce system change with varying degrees of impact (i.e. ranging from “shallow”, i.e. incremental changes, with only minor leverage on changing a system, to “deep”, i.e. transformative and disruptive). Therefore, the SUMEX project utilises the LP Model to map extractive sector practices according to their potential for system change towards sustainability. For more information on the application of the LP Model in the SUMEX project, please see Deliverable 3.1. this report.

- 1- Power and capacity to change worldviews
- 2- Worldviews in which the system is rooted
- 3- Goal and intent of the system
- 4- Power to change rules & structure of the system
- 5- Rules and Institutions to "operationalise" the new system
- 6- Structure of information flow & access to information
- 7- Strength of positive and reinforcing feedback loops
- 8- Strength of negative feedback loops to establish corrective actions
- 9- Length of delays in relation to the pace of the system change
- 10- Material stocks & flows
- 11- Size of buffer stocks and their stability
- 12- Parameters, metrics, numbers

Leverage points are points in the respective system at which even small changes can lead to significant change; hence they are referring to systems' change processes, in which a system is reorganising (e.g. towards sustainability) and enters a new state. Previous work has identified two specific processes in which LPs are emerging: (i) regime shifts, which are large-scale changes in structure and function of entire systems; and (ii) transformations, such as sustainability transformations, which are fundamental reorganisations of a system. Such change processes involve technologies, rules and structural change, attitudes, values and behaviour or knowledge- and information flows.

DELIVERABLE 2.2

P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	AA	AB	AC	AD
PLACEHOLDER: SD Good Practice -Sustainability Aspects			PLACEHOLDER: SD Good Practice - LEVERAGE POINT 1-12 scale											
SD - ENVIRONMENTAL "Environmental Sustainability" (i: water stewardship, ii: efficient energy consumption, iii: carbon neutrality, iv: air emissions, v: land use and biodiversity, vi: waste management)	SD - SOCIAL "Social and Societal Responsibility" (i: Shared vision partnerships, ii: stakeholder engagement, iii: human rights, iv: cultural heritage and FPIC, v: ethical practices, vi: transparency, vii: Diversity, inclusion & anti-discrimination, viii: workers' well-being)	SD - ECONOMIC "Transforming the Economy (i.e. considering the Green Deal" (i: role and indicators for an inclusive Green Economy, ii: valuing all forms of capital, iii: benefit sharing, iv: Accountability, v: Planning beyond the mine life, vi: Holistic risk management and emergency preparedness)	1 - power and capacity to change worldviews: -new sustainability narrative; - dematerialisation & full consumption reduction	2 - worldviews in which the system is rooted - societal pressure to adopt RS - valuing natural capital and using RS to protect it - focus on environmental and societal justice	3 - goal and intent of the system - role of extractive industry in green economy & planetary boundaries - planning beyond mine life - workers well-being	4 - power to change rules & structure of the system - self-organisation of mining communities - new forms of labour and organisation with the power to change the status quo	5 - Rules and Institutions to "operationalise" the new system - new business models - standard setting & compliance - SLO approaches and new channels of cooperation & community engagement	6 - structure of information flow & access to information - accountability and reporting practices - supply chain due diligence, supplier audits - transparency of operations	7 - strength of positive and reinforcing feedback loops - net positive impact on biodiversity and ecosystem services around mine sites	8 - Strength of negative feedback loops to establish corrective actions - divestment from the mining sector	9 - length of delays in relation to the pace of the system change - rate of mineral exploitation - monitoring systems and reports on environmental damage -	10 - Material stocks & flows - infrastructure in mining regions - water, material and energy flows	11 - size of buffer stocks and their stability - ground water table recovery - ability to recover land for post-mining land-use - recoverable ecosystems	12 - parameters, metrics, numbers - taxes -voluntary standards - CO2 emissions - biodiversity loss - dislocated communities

FIGURE 9: SCREENING AND MAPPING PROCESS

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable presents the methodology for WP2's screening and mapping process of sustainable practices and contributing knowledge items in extractives industry projects and sustainability policies. The inventory covers regional, national and EU level projects addressing the five SUMEX thematic areas (socio-economic and environmental impacts, land use planning, health & safety, reporting and permitting). In addition, selected industry and professional association practices and knowledge items from companies and organisations such as Anglo American, BHP, Rio Tinto, UEPG, ICMM and the Finnish Network of Sustainable Mining are included.

Currently, the inventory covers 275 data items, which will be uploaded to the SUMEX digital repository, the purpose of which is to initiate learning among practitioners and promote sustainability in the extractives sector. In the user-friendly online repository, practitioners can easily identify and learn about good practices from both the business and policy sphere. WP2 will continue to screen data items relevant for learning. Boliden's sustainability reports, OECD European case studies and the Joint Research Center's document on Environmental Impact Assessment are currently being screened and will be added to the inventory and uploaded to the online repository. Other practices that arise from ongoing research and industry projects during the course of the SUMEX project will also be assessed and included if considered suitable.

7 APPENDIX 1- DELIVERABLES SCREENED

Table 7 below shows all of the deliverables that have been screened to date including those at the EU level, national and regional projects as well as industry guidance and good practice documents.

TABLE 7: DELIVERABLES SCREENED

Screened projects	Screened Deliverables
H2020 2014-2015	
BioMore	Deliverable 5.3 Review of legislation and BREF documents for the environmentally safe exploitation of stimulated in situ bioleaching
FAME	D6.1 Report on Best-Practice Examples from Mining of Skarn, Greisen and Pegmatitic Ores (Utilisation of Processing Rejects)
HiTechAlkCarb	D6.1 Environmental and Social Assessment and Environmental Management Plan for drilling and geophysics at test site (Kaiserstuhl, Germany) New geomodels to explore deeper for High-Technology critical raw materials in Alkaline rocks and Carbonatites
INTRAW	D2.5 Action Plan to enhance cooperation on International Industrial & Trade Policies on Raw Materials
MICA	D5.1 Raw Materials Intelligence Tools and Methods
MINATURA2020	D2.2 Set of Qualifying Conditions for a Harmonised Mapping Framework (Hmf) for Each Type of Mineral D3.2 National/Regional Guidance on incorporating the MDoPI concept and qualifying conditions D3.3 Towards a European Vision for Mineral Deposits of Public Importance (Mdopi) in Europe D5.1 Guidelines for the implementation of the Stakeholder Participation Process
MINGUIDE	D4.3 Innovative Processing - Final report including guidelines and recommendations for future policy development for innovation in mineral and metallurgical processing D3.4 Innovative exploration and Extraction - Guidelines and Recommendations for future policy and legislation D5.3 Innovative Waste Management a Mine Closure - Final Report on innovative waste management and mine closure. Guidelines and recommendations for future policy and legislation development.
OptimOre	Deliverable D2.2: European CRM Perspective and Technology Selection
Real-Time-Mining	D9.1. Advanced Mine Monitoring Control, Operation and Safety System for Small Scale Mines
REGREEN	D2.1. Report on Assessment of Drivers and Pressures Leading to Urban Challenges, across The ULLs, Including Spatial and Temporal Components
UNEXMIN	D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Protocol
VAMOS	D4.2: Environmental Monitoring System – Final D1.3 Zero-state environmental and geo-hazard evaluation criteria

VERAM	Research and Innovation Roadmap 2050 (pl finished screening)
H2020 2016-2017	
BioDivScen	D6.3 Handbook on the use of biodiversity scenarios in support of decision-making
CHROMIC	D6.4 Community Involvement Plan
CIRCULAR IMPACTS	Insights from the CIRCULAR IMPACTS case studies
COLLECTORS	Deliverable 2.4 Report on solutions for tackling systemic and technical boundary conditions
FORAM	D4.3 Synthesis Report on Key Recommendations
IMPACT	D5.3 Re-thinking the concept of small-scale mining for a European context: features of modern technologically-advanced small-scale mining D5.5 Policy Statement, Standards and H&S Best Practice for SOSO Mining Operations
INFACT	D2.7 Environmental Impact and Social Acceptability D3.2 Guidance Notes for Exploration Best Practice in WP4 D3.3 Guidance Notes for Exploration Best Practice in WP5 D3.7 Choosing Socially and Environmentally More Acceptable Exploration Technologies D6.3 The INFACT Social Licence to Operate Index Model
ITERAMS	WP7 Clustering: Sustainability and Communication with local communities: D7.3: Final cluster workshop and policy recommendations
MinFuture	D5.3 A roadmap towards monitoring the physical economy
Minland	D2.1 Policy. A review of policies and practices throughout Europe on mineral resources and land use D.5.1 The Logical Framework Approach for integration of mineral resources into land-use planning
MIREU	D4.4 MIREU SLO Guidelines D4.5 MIREU SLO Toolbox
NEXT	D5.1 Key Factors Influencing Social License to Operate During the Mineral Exploration Phase D5.5 A Practical Toolkit addressed to Mineral Exploration and Mining Companies
ORAMA	Final report - Orama Project: Recommendations for wider implementation & policy briefs
PACIFIC	D1.3– Report comparing best practice in active and passive exploration methods
PLATIRUS	D1.6 Safety and Health Risk Management Procedures Report
REINVENT	Climate Innovations in the Steel Industry Deliverable 2.2
SCALE	D5.1 Environmental, health and safety controls that should be taken into account in SCALE technology development
SCREEN	D4.3 Circular Economy and zero waste aspects and business models of production (PL - not relevant as about characteristics of each CRM)
SecREETs	D33 Framework of the sustainability and risk assessment.
SIMS	D8.5 A guide of social management of new technology
SLIM	D10.1. Best Practices on Social Awareness Communication D10.2. Social awareness guidelines for local communities D10.3 Education Programme on Social Awareness D10.4 Report on use case results and recommendations

Smart Exploration	Deliverable D31 Exploitation Activities and Toolbox
X-MINE	Deliverable 3.2 Mineral-sorting algorithm test report - existing sensors
H2020 2018-2020	
CEWASTE	CEWASTE Project Final Report
CICERONE	T1.1 Overview of Raw Materials Sector in Circular Economy and Trends in Technology and Business Fields
DIGIECOQUARRY	Innovative Digital Sustainable Aggregates Systems
ILUCIDARE	D3.7 Coaching session and Training Modules for Heritage-led innovation and international relations
REGREEN	D7.1 Activity programme for the ULLs
Regional Projects	
Abenteuer Erzberg	Open pit mining at the Erzberg
ADRIANA	ADRIANA – Remote sensing detection of industrial recyclables in mine tailings
Africa Mining Vision	Transparent, equitable and optimal exploitation of mineral resources to underpin broad-based sustainable growth and socio-economic development
ARCHUB2	Arctic Network Hub
Arctic Geoinvest	Arctic Geoinvest (webpage)
Arctic Smartness projects	Arctic Industry and Circular Economy cluster (webpage)
ARIDuA	Autonomous robots and the Internet of Things in underground mining
BestBioPLA	BestBioPLA – Fully Bio-based PLA Composites with Long-term Durability
BioLeach	Innovative Bio-treatment of RM
Biopeitto	Biopeitto-projekti. Biohiilen hyödyntäminen kaivannaisjätteiden peittomateriaaleissa ja viherrakentamisessa (https://tupa.gtk.fi/raportti/arkisto/51_2020.pdf)
BioProLat	BioProLat – Reductive Bioprocessing to Recover Cobalt and Nickel From Laterites in Brazil
BrineMine – Extracting minerals and drinking water from geothermal sources in Chile"	BrineMine – Extracting minerals and drinking water from geothermal sources in Chile
BuSK	Local Acceptance of Industrial Operations Within Mining, Forestry, Fish Farming and Tourism in Lapland and Troms/Finnmark – Building Shared Knowledge Capital to Support Natural Resource Governance in the Northern Periphery
CAMaRSEC	CAMaRSEC – Climate-adapted Material Research for the Socio-economic Context in Vietnam
CaMona	Economical Extraction of Rare Earths from Secondary Raw Material Containing Monazite from the Greater Catalão Region
DAMAST	Technologies for the safe and efficient operation of water reservoirs
DIM ESEE 2	DIM ESEE-2 (website)
DUB-GEM	Aerial Mapping – Radioactive Contamination in Central Asia
EnEx	Enhanced exploration
FARMIN	Field Augmented Reality in Mineral Exploration and Mining
GloREIA	Towards a Global Rare Earth Industry Association

HoloMine	Mixed Reality in Mining
HybArkt	Passiiviset hybridipuhdistusratkaisut arktisten valumavesien tyypen ja raskasmetallien puhdistamiseen – HybArkt -hankkeen loppuraportti (Final Report)
IncluESEE	Inclusion of the ESEE region and Ukraine in innovative exploration developments
INCO-Piles-2020	International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RI
InnoLOG	Innovative geophysical logging tools for mineral exploration
INSPIRES	INtelligent and Sustainable Processing of Innovative Rare-Earth magnetS
InPhos	Sustainable Management of Phosphorus in Baltic countries
InvestRM	Decision-making tool for facilitating investment in the raw material sector
iTARG3T	Innovative targeting & processing of W-Sn-Ta-Li ores: towards EU's self-supply
iRIS	Intelligent Risk Identification System for safer mines
LINOKAS	Combined use of linseed and fibre straw
MaMMA	Maintained Mine & Machine
Mercury-AMF	Phytoremediation of Mercury-contaminated Mining Sites in Ghana and Burkina Faso Using Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi
MineService	Mining/Mineral Support Services
MoCa	Recovering rare earth elements
ReAK	Reduktion von Arsen in Kupferkonzentraten in Chile
ReCaLI	Recycling catalysts for use in oil refineries in Vietnam
REEBAUX	Prospects of REE recovery from bauxite and bauxite residue in the ESEE region
REGINA	Regional Innovation in the Nordic Arctic
REGINA	Rare earth global industry and new applications in Brazil
REMIX	<p>MineFacts</p> <p>The on-line database with geochemical maps of selected areas in Lower Silesia</p> <p>Revitalisation of a closed coal mine into a living science and art centre</p> <p>Lavrión Technological and Cultural Park (LTCP)</p> <p>Remediation of abandoned mines in Centro Region of Portugal: Urgeiriça uranium mining area example</p> <p>Establishing the Gold Mine tourist complex in Złoty Stok</p> <p>The Austrian Minerals Plan (AMRP)</p> <p>Mining heritage as a new purpose of Czech - Polish cross-border tourism</p> <p>The Man Engine</p> <p>Wheal Jane Earth Science Park: post-mining business regeneration</p> <p>Cornwall Mining Alliance</p> <p>SANTA BÁRBARA FOUNDATION: R&D and training for productivity and safety in the mining sector</p> <p>The Phocis Mining Park – Vagonetto</p> <p>Public provision of mining information by Austrian institutions</p> <p>Systematic thematic development of mining, metallurgy & raw materials conditions in the region</p> <p>Mining Lands Castilla y León– Program of actions for unemployed, companies and entrepreneurs</p>

	“Copper. A history of the extraordinary metal” exhibition in the Copper Museum in Legnica Coal Safari
ReWoRK	Recycling Tungsten from Ore Concentration Residues
RIS-ALiCE	Al-rich industrial residues for mineral binders in ESEE region
RIS-CuRe	Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region
RIS-RECOVER	Regional innovation scheme for zero waste extraction of critical raw materials
RM@School	Raw MatTERS Ambassadors at Schools
SAND!	SAND! – Alternative sand production and reducing risk of dredging in Vietnam
SecMinTec	Use of secondary sources of raw materials - tailings, mining waters, slags
SmartH ₂ OEnergy	Hydropower in the Peruvian raw materials industry
TRABBIO	Transforming Brazilian organic residue masses into recyclable materials and energy sources
UL2L— UrbanLinks 2 Landscape	Garzweiler - Recultivation of open cast mining Development of the Park Gródek area in Jaworzno:
RECORD	Railway industry as new opportunity for the coal mining region Regions in Europe Coordinate and Optimize innovation and competitiveness policy instruments towards improving the sustainability of transport - study case of SMEs in the railway sector
SYMBI: Industrial Symbiosis for Regional Sustainable Growth and a Resource Efficient Circular Economy	Reutilization of treated waste water
Industry Practices	
Kaivosvastuu	Water management Tailings Management Mine closure Performance Health & Safety Crisis Management Energy Use and GHG Emissions Biodiversity Management Community Outreach Performance
Anglo American	3A Stakeholder Engagement: Community Engagement Forum 3A Stakeholder Engagement: Stakeholder Engagement Plan 3B Incident and Grievance Management 3C Social and Human Rights Impact and Risk Analysis (SHIRA) 4A Socio-Economic Development (SED)
BHP	Environment and Climate Change - Our Requirements Safety - Our Requirements Health - Our Requirements Community - Our Requirements Code of Conduct
ICMM	Global Industry Standard on Tailings Management A Practical Guide to Consistent Water Reporting (2017) Integrated Mine Closure Good Practice Guidance on Occupational Health Risk Assessment

	<p>Health and Safety performance Indicators Mining Principles Optimising mining’s partnering capability to contribute to community resilience and thriving societies Tool for Closure Electrification of their transportation systems</p>
<p>UEPG</p>	<p>Case Study: Recycling of process water in protection zone for groundwater supply Case Study: Conversion of a quarry into a natural zone, while maintaining and increasing biodiversity Case Study: Restoration of a sand and gravel quarry to a number of lakes, each creating a different habitat. Case study: To mitigate potential impacts of the development of a quarry Case Study: To combine the needs of extraction sites with nature protection areas. To prove the positive impact of extracting activities on biodiversity. Case Study: community-based environmental restoration Case Study: Develop the ecological potential of the quarry in the area of « la Bassée » while preserving water resources of the site and the local natural heritage. Case study: Quarzsand Nudersdorf - Improvement of the biodiversity through the example of the open cast quartz sand mine Case study: Brett Aggregates - Restoration of sand and gravel extraction sites to woodland, landscaped lakes and heathland Case study: ALAS SLOVAKIA s.r.o. - The conservation of a protected bird territory no. 20 “Morava” (Moravia) and nature protection of flood territory utilising sedimentation of sludge pits. Case study: PREBETONG ÁRIDOS SLU - GRUPO VOTORANTIM - The restoration of the gravel extraction area after the end of the exploitation Case study: LafargeHolcim - To make extraction compatible with the management of biodiversity Case study: CERF SAS - Minimising the impact on the aquatic life and morphology of the ecosystem through the recycling of the water usage during the process Case study: GSM (Italcementi Group) - Developing the ecological potential of an alluvial quarry located in the valley of Seine, upriver from Fontainebleau. Case study: Wopfinger Transportbeton GesmbH - Optimising the measures currently foreseen for nature and species protection to be effectively realised during and after the extraction Case study: COLAS HRVATSKA d.d - Restoration of a former gravel extraction site for a recreational purpose</p>

8 APPENDIX 2- ADDITIONAL DELIVERABLES POTENTIALLY TO BE SCREENED

Table 8 below shows additional deliverables that will be reviewed for relevance and potentially screened in the future.

TABLE 8: DELIVERABLES YET TO BE SCREENED

Projects	Deliverables yet to be screened
	H2020 2014-2015
BioMore	D 6.2 Report on stakeholder assessment processed during two stakeholder workshops D6.6 Brochures, leaflets and newsletter and film D6.8 Report summarising dialogue activities and results with user groups
BlueNodules	D1.7 Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) components for test mining up to prototype level D5.10 Guidelines and recommendations for environmental monitoring
HiTechAlkCarb	D6.2 Paper on Environmental and Social Assessment D6.3 Lessons learned: Challenges in geological scientific fieldwork at the Kaiserstuhl carbonatite, Germany
INTRAW	D2.4 Action plan to enhance international education and outreach activities on raw materials D4.6 Press-releases and media kits concerning INTRAW initiatives and outcomes
METGROWPLUS	D3.6 Report on metal extraction of low-grade ores and wastes
MICA	D2.1 Stakeholder Report: identification & analysis D3.4 & 4.4 Integrating data, methods and expert knowledge to inform mineral intelligence D4.3 Case Studies D5.6 Report on RMI implementation status quo and needs in EU-28
MINATURA2020	D3.1 Multi-Sectoral analysis of mineral policies and land use policies in EU countries D4.2 Results of testing the proposed MDoPI assignment methodology & harmonised mapping framework (HMF)
MINGUIDE	D1.3 Guidance for EU and MS mineral policy and legislation D2.2 Minerals policy governance in Europe: good practice examples in EU Member States D3.2 Innovative exploration and Extraction - Innovation evaluation criteria and best case practices in Exploration and Extraction D5.2 Innovative Waste Management and Mine Closure - Report on innovation evaluation criteria and best case practices in waste management and mine closure
OptimOre	Deliverable D10.1: Project website
Real-Time-Mining	D2.3 Catalogue of Sustainability and Industrial Viability Indicators (SPI) specifically related to REAL-TIME-MINING including a description of required sensor functionality, precision and accuracy needed to quantify SPIs Real-Time-Mining newsletter

ROBUST	D9.3 Project Newsletter
STRADE	European Policy Brief - Africa & the European Union – Renewing Sustainable Partnerships in the Extractives Sector European Policy Brief - Aligning EU cooperation with resource-rich developing and emerging countries’ needs Concept for a data and knowledge information system on mineral mining and trade and related environmental and socio- economic issues 1.0 STRADE Final report European Policy Brief - Operational design and implementation experience with due diligence initiatives and certification schemes European Policy Brief - Platforms for strategic dialogue on mining and minerals: a possible way forward Supporting the EU Mineral Sector - Capitalising on EU strengths through an investment promotion strategy European Policy Brief - Voluntary initiatives in the mining sector and their principles and criteria on environmental sustainability
UNEXMIN	D8.7 Scientific publications, presentations, posters D8.16 Research roadmap
VAMOS	D6.6: Future Research Roadmap (Final) D6.5: Policy Recommendations report (final)
H2020 2016-2017	
COP21 RIPPLES	D3.2 Report on energy security implications of NDC and 2°C/1.5°C trajectories D3.4 Report on competitiveness, trade, and industrial implications of the INDCs and 2°C /1.5°C mitigation pathways
CROCODILE	D7.9 Standardisation of mobile plant D7.8 Standardisation of stationary plant
EUCalc	D3.1 Raw materials module and manufacturing and secondary raw materials module for EUCalc D4.2 Expert consultation workshop on land, land use and carbon stock dynamics (LULUCF), biomass provision (food, energy, materials) & minerals
FORAM	D2.2 Report on outcomes stakeholder consultation and options for better international cooperation D3.1 Global raw materials policy context report D4.1 Roadmap for the establishment of a world forum on raw materials
IMPACT	D2.5 Paper: Best Practice D2.7 Water quality manuscript D2.8 Environmental Impact Assessment for stibnite-quartz deposits D5.2 Policy briefing document D5.7 Integrating social Life cycle analysis into SOSO mining
INFACT	D2.5 Feedback report from local landowners and communities on test site plans and analysis of test site engagement practices D3.4 Environmental Impacts and Social Acceptability Information for T4. - part 1&2 D3.6 Leveraging improvements to public acceptance of exploration methods via education

	<p>D3.11 Discovery Roadmap & Best Practices</p> <p>D6.7 Business model mechanism: ease of use; visitor best practice; relevance to industry; Budget – part 2</p> <p>D7.13 Report on activities for on education, lifelong learning, wider society and professional education</p>
INNOPATHS	<p>D1.4 Socio-Technical Analysis Report</p> <p>D2.4 Report on the sectoral and national (plus EU) innovation system case studies</p>
Intermin	<p>D2.2 Integrated competency model for employment across the raw material sector</p> <p>D2.3 Roadmap on skills provisioning for the raw material sector</p> <p>D3.1 International qualification framework for the raw materials sector</p> <p>D3.3 Best practice guidelines for training in the raw materials sector</p>
ITERAMS	<p>Short project book including main findings of the demonstrators and LCA</p>
MinFuture	<p>D3.2 Concise description of application fields for different MFA approaches and indicators</p> <p>D5.1 A systems approach for the monitoring of the physical economy</p> <p>D5.2 Testing of the Framework</p> <p>D6.4.1 MinFuture Policy Brief</p>
Minland	<p>D4.1: Existing valorisation and classification schemes and valuation methods for mineral land use practices</p> <p>D4.4 Civil society`s influence on land use practise across Europe</p> <p>D.5.2 Stakeholder involvement in applying a common framework on natural resources</p> <p>D.5.3 Promoting a common framework as tool for societal risk management and risk displacement tool</p> <p>D.5.4 – Indicators for successful integration of a common framework on natural resources planning</p> <p>D.6.1 Common approach for peer learning and good practice guidance</p> <p>D6.2: Final Manual for Good Practice Guidance</p>
MIREU	<p>D3.1 Review of the applicable regulatory and policy conditions in the MIREU regions</p> <p>D4.1 Regional cultural identity and stakeholder mapping report</p> <p>SWOT analysis of regions and valorisation of mining heritage (no access)</p> <p>MIREU SLO Benchmarking Report</p>
NEMO	<p>D4.1 Report on legislative/regulative requirements for transport and processing of mining residues in the EU and construction product standards and certification procedures</p>
ORAMA	<p>D3.5: Navigating environmental & social knowledge</p> <p>D3.4: Serving environmental & social spatial data</p>
PLATIRUS	<p>D8.1 Value Chain Stakeholders Analysis</p>
Removal	<p>D 2.1 Laboratory tests on alkali recovery and red mud dealkalisation for different BR</p>

SCREEN	<p>D4. Production technologies of CRM from secondary resources</p> <p>D4.1 Production technologies of CRM from primary</p> <p>D8.2 Upgrading regulations and standards to enable recycling of CRM from WEEE</p> <p>D10.8 Report on engagement with the general public and recommendations for future actions</p> <p>D6.4 Roadmap and innovation pathways for technology development in CRMs value chains to unlock primary and secondary unexploited resources and introduce substitution solutions in industry</p> <p>D6.3 Technological gaps hindering uptake of CRMs substitution in industrial application</p> <p>D7.3 Impact of (voluntary) standards, policies and regulatory frameworks on CRM value chains including those for substitution</p> <p>D7.2 Report on (voluntary) standards, policies and regulatory frameworks in Europe relevant to CRMs</p> <p>D1.1 Plan for a transparent consultation of stakeholders</p>
SIMS	<p>D3.17 Evaluation and exploitation actions for novel mine communication phase 3</p> <p>D5.7 Evaluation and Exploitation Actions of SIMS in Robotics for Mines</p> <p>D7.8 Evaluation of SIMS Ground Control Contributions to European Mining</p>
SLIM	D10.4 Report on use case results and recommendations
H2020 2018-2020	
CICERONE	<p>D1.2 Report on current state of the art & understanding of the Circular Economy</p> <p>CICERONE - Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda on Circular Economy</p>
ILUCIDARE	<p>D3.8 Capacity Building implementation guidelines</p> <p>D3.9 Overview report on Regulatory, Economic and Technical barriers for heritage-led innovation and diplomacy in Europe</p>
LOCOMOTION	D8.1 Review of Policy Options to drive societies towards sustainability
REGREEN	<p>D2.1 Report on Assessment of drivers and pressures leading to urban challenges, across the ULLs, including spatial and temporal components</p> <p>D3.1 Synthesis report on current datasets and their applicability of ecosystem services mapping and modelling</p> <p>D6.1 Research protocol for the analysis of governance systems in European ULLs</p>
Regional Projects	
Mine Life	Intensification of institutional cooperation and partnership between citizens and institutions in all areas of public life for the development of the cross border area
SusMinNor	Synthesis Report Sustainable Mining – Nordic Advanced Knowledge Synthesis Guidebook Good Practises and Knowledge Gaps
Industry Practices	
Rio Tinto	Biodiversity protection and natural resource management standard

	<p>Business integrity standard Our approach to closure Communities and social performance standard Competition standard Disclosure and Communications Policy Employment Policy Hazardous materials and non-mineral waste management standard Our approach to health management Health, Safety, Environment and Communities Human rights policy Inclusion & diversity policy Industry associations and climate change Land management and rehabilitation standard Management of tailings and water storage standard Noise exposure control standard Process safety standard Radiation exposure control standard Role of civil society organisations Our approach to safety Rio Tinto – The way we work Transparency statement Underground safety standard Water quality protection and water management standard Why agreements matter: a resource guide for integrating agreements into Communities and Social Performance work at Rio Tinto Why cultural heritage matters: a resource guide for integrating cultural heritage management into Communities work at Rio Tinto Why gender matters: A resource guide for integrating gender considerations into Communities work at Rio Tinto Why human rights matter: a resource guide for integrating human rights into Communities and Social Performance work at Rio Tinto</p>
<p>Anglo American</p>	<p>The Social Way Toolkit: 4B Contractor Social Management 4C Community Health and Safety Management 4D Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning 4E Security Management & the Voluntary Principles on Security and Human Rights (VPSHR) 4F Land Access, Displacement and Resettlement 4G Site-Induced Migration (SIM) 4H Cultural Heritage 4I Indigenous Peoples 4J Conflict Management 4K Artisanal and Small-Scale Mining (ASM)</p>
<p>ICMM</p>	<p>Closure Maturity Framework (2020) Global Industry Standard on Tailings Management (2020) Mining as a Partner in Supporting More Inclusive and Resilient Societies (2020, about COVID – health and safety?) Adapting to a Changing Climate: Building resilience in the mining and metals industry (2019)</p>

DELIVERABLE 2.2

	Company-Community Relations: Training materials
Boliden	<p>Minimizing environmental impact with volcanic clay</p> <p>Extracting zinc through steel mill dust recycling at Rönnskär</p> <p>Landfilled sulphur residue set to be Kokkola's next resource</p> <p>Sustainable water management at Boliden</p> <p>Kokkola jarosite research</p> <p>Purification of manganese from anode sludge at Kokkola</p> <p>Converting secondary materials from electronics into precious metals at Harjavalta</p> <p>Climate smart transports</p> <p>Smart battery storage for a safer electricity supply</p> <p>When the environment and economy both win</p> <p>Contributing to a circular economy at Kokkola</p> <p>Mine automation improves safety</p> <p>Dead wood brings forest to life</p> <p>Largest electronic material recycler in the world</p> <p>Scrap lead batteries recycled to new raw material</p> <p>Gillervattnet reclamation project</p> <p>Reducing waste and enhancing profitability</p> <p>Fjord clean up at the Odda smelter</p> <p>Safety culture and business stability go hand in hand</p> <p>Worker health initiatives: The Kokkola approach</p>

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https://www.sumexproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/SUMEX_MUL_D_1.2_SD-criteria.pdf

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D2.1 – CLUSTERING WORKSHOPS: LESSONS LEARNED AND KEY TAKEAWAYS

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D3.1 - ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK